

Long-Term Ultrasound Detectability of Tumor site Marker: Developing a Novel *in vivo* Marker

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*Abstract: Breast cancer is currently detected early und requires very often a wire localization - a procedure that uses a fine wire to mark the exact location of a lump or abnormality - before a surgeon does an excisional biopsy to remove the lump. A wire localization is also required when a "Preoperative Systemic Treatment" (PST) of breast cancer has been administered before surgery. Wire localization can be avoided when an ultrasound guided surgery is an option. A long-term ultrasound detectability of the tumor site marker is prerequisite when a PST is planned and ultrasound guided surgery is an option. In this project, we investigate the development of a novel long-term ultrasound detectable *in vivo* tumor site marker.*

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I. Introduction

The market for medical implants, modern devices and materials is constantly increasing as a result of new knowledge, experience and the possibility of individualized treatment [1]. Tumor site markers help physicians in communicating with each other and are a prerequisite for radiological or ultrasound guided surgical treatment or follow up of tumors under medical treatment. Tumor site markers must therefore be easily detectable radiologically and in ultrasound. They have to be biocompatible and need to be insertable via puncture through medical canula. Most national health systems are overwhelmed with the cost of commercially available products [2]. Biocompatibility of the materials, prevention of migration, ensuring visibility of the markers in mammography, and sonography and interference with imaging in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are important issues [3].

Radiologically, the detection of biopsy site markers or clips has not been a major challenge. But the problem with long-term ultrasound detectability has in fact not been answered adequately. Biopsy site markers and clips or markers currently used in breast radiology come in countless shapes and sizes, and almost all of them are metallic (Fig. 1). Design and manufacture of a plastic with biocompatible characteristics that can be visualized via ultrasound over an extended period of time is a challenging task. Pure polymers with low reflectivity are not visible in ultrasound, so the morphology of the samples and the selection of materials with reflective properties are very important factors [4]. There is some new research work in the field of surface roughness, ultrasonic properties and visibility enhancement by color Doppler [5].

Nevertheless, it could be argued that color Doppler is not the optimal tool for surgical applications. In order to make

an informed decision, it is essential to consider a number of additional factors, including material selection, biological properties, manufacturing process, design, cost, and ultrasound detectability. Furthermore, it is of paramount importance to assess the radiological detectability and potential interference in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).

Figure 1: Wire localization of a tumor site marker before surgery after PST. The tumor itself is no longer detectable (above). Ex vivo Tissue radiograph showing tumor site marker and localization wire.

II. Material and methods

The objective of this study is to evaluate the visibility of polymer and composite markers in radiological and ultrasound imaging using biocompatible components. A variety of potential markers have been developed and tested, as detailed in Table 1. The PMMA marker was manufactured using Zimmer Biomet bone cement, which was sourced from Heraeus Medical Germany. The PEEK and PEEK-carbon fiber samples were produced using a fused deposition modelling (FDM) system. Carbon fibers were inserted to improve the image in ultrasound images due to impedance difference with the body tissue. Figure 2 depicts the embedded sample, which comprises polymer PEEK with a 30% of carbon fiber. Subsequently, the markers were implanted in bovine gelatin at a consistent distance. Prior to this, however, a series of tests were conducted utilizing standard ultrasonic devices (Echograph 1095). The amplitude and depth of the sample in the gelatin matrix were then assessed using ultrasonic reflection waves, which allowed a more accurate assessment of the position of the sample in the gelatin matrix. The samples were embedded in gelatin in both vertical and longitudinal sections. To assess the practical visibility of the samples from a medical end-user's perspective, a series of samples were analyzed ex vivo in an experimental setup developed by a team of breast cancer surgeons using a state-of-the-art medical ultrasound machine (Samsung HS60). Computed tomography (CT) scans were then performed to determine the number of detectable pores or potential defects.

Figure 2: Cross-section of an embedded sample of PEEK polymer with 30% carbon fibers.

Table 1: Font size and format.

Sample Nr.	Material
1	PEEK 450G
2	PEKK 450G- CF30
3	Bone cements PMMA

III. Results and discussion

Following ultrasonic examination, it was determined that samples composed of PEKK 450G- CF30 composites exhibited a higher reflectivity, indicated by a percentage of back wall signal height (BSH) of 59%. This finding suggests that the samples are more visible and have a higher

reflectivity than bone cement, which demonstrated a BSH of only 14%. It is noteworthy that the samples exhibited greater reflectivity in the longitudinal direction than in the vertical. This can be attributed to the larger surface area available for the reflected wave in this position, which allows for greater reflection. The medical ultrasound image of sample 2 in Fig. 3, prepared using PEEK with carbon fiber, also displays a visible illustration, as can be observed.

Figure 3: The medical ultrasound image of the sample 2 prepared from the PEEK with carbon fiber.

The initial sample, comprising solely PEEK, was subjected to radiographic analysis, as illustrated in Fig. 4. The volume of pores and voids was determined to be 3.08%.

Figure 4: The figure illustrates the pores and cavities of sample 1 following an X-radiographic examination. The pore volume is 3.08%. The largest pore has a diameter of approximately 300 μm .

The formation of pores within the PEEK samples can be attributed to the combination of elevated temperatures and humidity content. PEEK exhibits a tendency to absorb humidity from the surrounding environment and atmosphere. As indicated by the manufacturer, the bone cement in question contains 15% zirconium dioxide, which is highly beneficial for the visualization of the sample under X-ray examination.

IV. Conclusions

The visibility of materials under ultrasound or the ability to receive high-intensity focused ultrasound depends on the reflectivity, permeability, and shape of the material in question. Consequently, a composite of different materials represents an optimal result for components of the research project, such as PEEK with carbon fibers or bone cement (PMMA) with the modification of ingredients. FDM as the simplest production method has the potential to be further investigated as a means of replacing the material content to achieve long-term visibility under ultrasound over a long period of time and to demonstrate biocompatibility.

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The study was designed by Mohammad Masafi and Soheil Pilehvar, who were also responsible for its implementation and planning. The data obtained from the experiment were subjected to analysis, and the resulting manuscript was prepared accordingly.

Prof. Dr. Hadi Mozaffari-Jovein, Head of Institute of Materials Science and Engineering Tuttlingen, Furtwangen University, and Dr. med. Hamid Huschmand Nia, Head of Breast Cancer Center and Gynecological Oncology at Marienhaus Klinikum Hetzelstift, supervised the project.

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